

Solvent Extraction Behaviour of Lead(II) with Versatic 911

UDAY SANKAR RAY* and S. C. MODAK

Department of Chemistry, Visva Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235

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Extraction of lead(II) with liquid cation exchanger, Versatic 911, in benzene, toluene or *n*-hexane from 0.1 *M* acetate solution has been investigated. Quantitative extraction has been achieved in the pH range 5.5-6.0. Nitric acid (2 *M*) is used for stripping the metal ion from the organic phase. The effect of pH, extractant concentration, acetate ion concentration and contact time on extraction of lead has been studied. The role of different diluents on extraction at different pH are discussed. The probable composition of the extracted species, $PbR_{2.2}RH$ ($RH=$ Versatic 911) is derived from the extraction results.

In the last few years considerable interest has developed in the extraction of metals with commercial organic extractants. Among them, acidic organophosphorous esters and carboxylic acids behave as liquid cation exchanger. A large amount of work on the extraction of metals with carboxylic acid has been carried out and results have been published in a number of recent papers. In our laboratory, we have extensively studied the extraction behaviour of cerium(IV), thorium(IV) and uranium(VI) with Versatic 9, Versatic 10 and Versatic 911¹⁻³. A survey of literature revealed that very little work has been done on the extraction behaviour of lead(II) with Versatic acids⁴. Fletcher and Flett⁵ reported the extraction of lead(II) with naphthenic acid. Tanaka *et al*⁶ studied the extraction of lead(II) with capric acid and determined the composition of the extracted species. The present study was undertaken to investigate the extraction behaviour of lead(II) from an aqueous solution of constant ionic strength into Versatic 911, diluted with benzene, toluene or *n*-hexane.

Experimental

An Elico pH meter, Model LI-10, was used for the measurement of pH.

Versatic 911 is a mixture of saturated tertiary monocarboxylic acids of C_9 , C_{10} and C_{11} chain length, manufactured from C_9-C_{11} olefines. This was supplied by Shell Chemical Co., London and was used without further purification. The concentration and purity of the supplied Versatic 911 are 5.43 *M* and 99.0%, respectively⁷. Versatic 911 was standardized by usual acid-alkalimetric titration. A large number of solutions of Versatic 911 of different strengths were prepared by diluting it with benzene, toluene or *n*-hexane.

A stock solution of lead acetate (9.74 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving $Pb(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ (A.R.) in 0.1 *M* acetic acid and was standardized by complexometric titration with EDTA (disodium salt)

using xylenol orange indicator⁸. All other chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade.

General procedure : Aliquots of the aqueous and the organic solutions, 20 ml and 10 ml, respectively were introduced into 250 ml separatory funnels. Dilute sodium hydroxide solution was used for adjustment of pH. The extraction experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ by manual shaking to give maximum mixing of the phases. The initial metal concentration in the aqueous phase was 2.35×10^{-3} *M* and the ionic strength of the aqueous phase was kept constant (10^{-1} *M* acetate). The two phases were equilibrated for sufficient time to ensure complete equilibrium. The general procedure of phase separation and stripping of the organic phase was similar to that described earlier¹. The metal ion from the organic phase was stripped with 20 ml 2 *M* nitric acid and estimated by complexometric titration⁹.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variables on extraction :

pH :

The comparative extraction behaviour of lead(II) with Versatic 911 in benzene, toluene or *n*-hexane at different pH has been investigated. The extractions were carried out at different concentrations of Versatic 911. It was observed that the extraction of lead(II) (2.35×10^{-3} *M*) increases with increased pH and increased extractant concentration. The extraction becomes quantitative at pH 5.5-6.0 with 1.63 *M* Versatic 911 in benzene, toluene and *n*-hexane. At higher pH ($pH > 6.0$) lead undergoes hydrolysis which leads to difficulty in phase separation. To prevent hydrolysis at higher pH all the extraction experiments were carried out in presence of 0.1 *M* acetate. Both aliphatic and aromatic diluents show almost similar extraction behaviour of lead(II) with Versatic 911. The distribution ratio, *D*, and the percentage extraction of lead(II) at different pH are given in Table I.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF LEAD(II) WITH VERSATIC 911 AS A FUNCTION OF pH

Extractant	DILUENTS								
	Benzene			Toluene			n-Hexane		
	pH	Pb(II) extracted %	Distribution ratio D	pH	Pb(II) extracted %	Distribution ratio D	pH	Pb(II) extracted %	Distribution ratio D
Versatic 911 (1.63 M)	3.07	7.18	0.15	3.10	6.95	0.15	3.05	6.19	0.13
	3.65	34.08	1.03	3.65	33.86	1.02	3.75	35.84	1.12
	4.00	55.16	2.46	4.50	82.51	9.44	4.60	82.30	9.30
	4.55	82.52	9.44	4.95	94.84	36.76	5.15	95.58	43.25
	5.15	96.64	57.52	5.40	98.65	146.15	5.60	98.67	143.38
	5.50	98.20	109.11	5.90	99.10	220.22	5.90	98.89	178.18
	5.80	99.10	220.20						
Versatic 911 (0.81 M)	3.00	1.79	0.04	3.05	1.35	0.01	3.05	3.76	0.08
	3.65	10.31	0.23	3.70	10.31	0.23	3.75	9.73	0.22
	4.50	48.43	1.88	4.55	50.22	2.02	4.60	47.35	1.80
	5.00	77.58	6.92	4.95	75.34	6.11	5.00	75.66	6.22
	5.40	92.15	23.48	5.45	94.39	33.65	5.50	94.03	31.50
	5.90	98.20	109.11	5.90	98.21	109.73	5.90	97.79	88.50
Versatic 911 (0.54 M)	3.10	1.35	0.03	3.07	0.45	0.01	3.05	1.33	0.03
	3.70	5.83	0.12	3.75	5.38	0.11	3.75	3.10	0.06
	4.55	27.80	0.77	4.50	24.66	0.66	4.55	25.22	0.68
	4.95	57.40	2.70	4.90	52.47	2.21	5.05	65.49	3.80
	5.40	84.75	11.12	5.40	84.75	11.12	5.40	85.40	11.70
	5.95	95.52	42.64	5.90	96.41	53.71	5.95	95.13	39.07
Versatic 911 (0.11 M)	3.65	0	0	3.62	0.45	0.01	3.60	0	0
	4.55	1.79	0.04	4.50	1.35	0.03	4.30	1.33	0.03
	5.05	6.95	0.15	5.05	5.83	0.12	4.85	2.21	0.05
	5.55	32.74	0.97	5.55	30.49	0.88	5.35	10.18	0.23
	5.75	52.91	2.25	6.00	65.02	3.72	5.70	34.96	1.08
	6.00	69.73	4.61				6.05	62.39	3.32

Equilibration times :

The effect of contact time on extraction and stripping of lead(II) has been studied. It was observed that both extraction and back-extraction is completed within 5 min. Nitric acid (2 M) is used for stripping the metal ion from the organic phase.

Acetate ion concentration :

The extraction dependence of lead(II) upon acetate ion concentration shows that extraction decreases with increase in acetate ion in the aqueous phase. The experiments were carried out at constant pH, constant metal ion concentration ($2.35 \times 10^{-3} M$) and constant extractant concentration (1.63 M) using the three different diluents. It was observed that under all these conditions log D is proportional to log [acetate], the slope of the logarithmic curves being around 2, indicating the release of two acetate ion in the extraction process.

Extractant concentration :

The extraction dependency of lead(II) on extractant concentration using the three different diluents was examined and the results are shown in Fig. 1. The experiments were carried out at constant metal concentration ($2.35 \times 10^{-3} M$), constant acetate ion concentration (0.1 M) and constant pH (5.0 or 5.5). The results show that the rate of extraction increases with the increase of extractant concentration when all other variables were kept constant.

Fig. 1. The dependence of D for lead(II) ($2.35 \times 10^{-3} M$) on extractant concentration. Other eluents (toluene and benzene) gave similar results. [O, pH 5.5 ; ●, pH 5]

Probable extraction mechanism :

Plot of log D against log [Versatic 911] at constant pH (5.0 or 5.5), constant metal concentration ($2.35 \times 10^{-3} M$) and constant acetate ion concentration (0.1 M) produced straight lines with slopes around 2 in all the systems. Shigematsu *et al*⁹ showed that Versatic 911 in non-polar diluents exists as a dimer. Taking this into consideration, it can be inferred that four Versatic 911 molecules are involved in the extracted species. So neglecting the part played by water, the probable extraction

mechanism can therefore be proposed as :

where the barred species are in the organic phase, R_2H_2 refers to the dimeric form of Versatic 911.

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